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WP3-T8 New. Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE/AE.

WP3-T8-ST1 New. Species/genotypes of *E. granulosus s.l.* causing human CE in Europe (2000-2021).

[Published] This systematic review (SR) aimed to fill a gap of knowledge by providing a quantitative measure of molecularly identified species and genotypes belonging to *E. granulosus s.l.* causing human CE in Europe during the period 2000-2021. From a total of 1,643 scientific papers, 51 records were included in the SR. The main inclusion criterion for this study was the molecular confirmation of Eg at the genotype/species level as a causative agent of human CE cases in selected European countries. Relevant data were obtained from 29 out of 39 eligible European countries. This SR identified 599 human molecularly confirmed echinococcal cysts: 460 (76.8%) identified as *E. granulosus s.s.*, 130 (21.7%) as *E. canadensis* cluster (G6/7 and G10), 7 (1.2%) as *E. ortleppi* (G5), and 2 as *E. vogeli* (0.3%). Three geographical hotspots of human CE caused by different species of the Eg complex were identified: (1) *E. granulosus s.s.* in Southern and South-eastern Europe (European-Mediterranean and Balkan countries); (2) *E. canadensis* (G6/7) in Central and Eastern Europe; (3) *E. ortleppi* in Central and Western Europe. This SR also identified data gaps that prevented a better definition of the geographical distribution of the Eg species complex in Europe: western Balkan countries, part of Central Europe and Baltic countries.

Figure 1. Approximate geographical distribution of species and genotypes of *E. granulosus s.l.* infecting humans (N=597) in Europe during 2000-2021. Prevalences of species and genotypes are reported in red.

WP3-T8-ST2 New. Unveiling the impact of human CE in Europe (1997-2021). **[Published]**

Although human CE is a notifiable parasitic infectious disease in most European countries, in practice it is largely under-reported by national health systems. To fill this gap, we extracted data on the number, incidence, and trend of human cases in Europe through a systematic review approach, using both the scientific and grey literature and accounting for the period of publication from 1997 to 2021. The highest number of possible human cases at the national level was calculated from various data sources to generate a descriptive model of human CE in Europe. We identified 64,745 human CE cases from 40 European countries. The mean annual incidence from 1997 to 2020 throughout Europe was 0.64 cases per 100,000 people and in EU member states was 0.50/100,000. Based on incidence rates and trends detected in this study, the current epicentre of cystic echinococcosis in Europe is in the south-eastern European countries, whereas historical endemic European Mediterranean countries have recorded a decrease in the number of cases over the time.

Figure 2. Number of documented human CE cases (N=64,745) in Europe at the national level during 1997-2021.

Figure x. Time-trend analysis of the number of human CE cases at the country level (observed cases and predicted cases for the years 2020-2024).

WP3-T8-ST3 New. Human source attribution of cerebral cystic echinococcosis (CCE) by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature. [Ms in preparation]

This activity focuses on the first source attribution based on molecular methods of a rare case of cerebral CE (CCE) in a child from Roman countryside. In 2019, a 6-year-old boy living in Roman countryside underwent a left frontal-parietal craniotomy and microsurgical removal of an echinococcal lesion. Cyst sample was collected together with 12 cyst samples, belonging to sheep from the same farm owned by the child's family (farm A), as well as from randomly collected from slaughtered sheep raised in a different farm (farm B) located in the same province. All 13 cyst samples were identified as *E. granulosus* s.s. with an RFLP method (Santolamazza et al., 2020) and DNA was used as template for the amplification of the partial mitochondrial genes COX1, NAD5, NAD2 and NAD1 (Kim et al., 2017; Kinkar et al., 2018). Concatenated sequences (2368 bp) were aligned and analysed to generate a TCS network. Results showed a clear genetic relationship between the child's cyst and the cysts belonging to the sheep of his own family's farm (farm A) (Figure x), in particular two sheep cyst sequences were identical to those of the child, thus supporting the hypothesis of a direct transmission within the family farm. A literature search was also conducted on 6 databases with Boolean terms for the clinical and epidemiological quantification of CCE at global level. The search identified 1,776 relevant articles which were selected by title and abstract. This SR identified 2,237 cases of human CCE of which 80.72% were primary cases, while 19.28% were secondary cases. Single CCE was detected in 83.85% of cases and multiple CCE in 16.15%. Of 1,587 cases for which data on age was present, 57.03% were ≤18 years, while 42.97 were >18 years. Of 1,709 CCE cases for which data on sex was present, 56.76% were males and 43.24% were females. Cyst rupture occurred in 12.25% of cases, recurrence in 9.7%, permanent disability in 7.78%, while death occurred in 6.21% (139/2,237). Considering clinical centres reporting any localization of CE, CCE occurred in 1.85% (110/7,829) of these cases.

Figure 3. Haplotype network of the concatenated sequences of the genes COX1, NAD5, NAD2 and NAD1 from 13 samples of *E. granulosus* including child cyst (green), sheep cysts from farm A (orange) and sheep cysts from farm B (pink), and five reference sequences from France, Spain, Turkey (G3), Albania and Italy (G1).

WP3-T8-ST4 New. Molecular and clinical epidemiology studies in selected geographical areas.

A) Human CE in the Kurdistan region, Iraq: characteristics and molecular identification. [Published]

From 2019 to 2021, 64 echinococcal cysts were surgically removed from 62 patients in Azadi and Vajeen reference Hospitals at Duhok city, Duhok governorate (Kurdistan region, Iraq). The results confirmed the liver as the most common anatomical site of CE with 72.58% of the cases, followed by the lungs in 19.35%, while 66.13% of CE cases were females. The highest rate of infections occurred in the age class 21–30 (27.42%). High rates of CE were reported among patients living in rural areas and housewives, which were 54.84% and 43.55% of the CE patients, respectively. The fertility of echinococcal cysts was 82.81%, and the viability of fertile protoscoleces was 70.53%. Cysts were staged

with ultrasound according to the WHO-IWGE classification as 32.8% CE1, 32.8% CE2, 7.8% CE3a, 9.4% CE3b, 15.6% CE4 and 1.6% CE5. Molecular analyses using mitochondrial NAD5 gene showed that all analyzed samples (n=59) belonged to the genotypes G1 or G3 of *E. granulosus s.s.*, thus, confirming sheep–dog–human transmission in the Kurdistan region, Iraq. No statistically significant correlation was found between the genotypes G1–G3 of *E. granulosus s.s.* and variables, such as the fertility, location and cyst stage classification. Based on the present findings, it is necessary to implement monitoring and control programs in sheep and dog populations to decrease the odds of human infections. Public health education campaigns are required to be implemented at the community level to reduce the risk of acquiring CE in humans in the Kurdistan region, Iraq.

B) A Retrospective cohort study on human CE in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (Pakistan) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records. [Published]

Human CE is a worldwide-distributed parasitic zoonotic disease, which represents a threat for both human and animals. The current study aimed at estimating the prevalence of human CE in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) province of Pakistan. Clinical records from four major hospitals in this region were reviewed for CE human cases during the period of 2006–2021. Out of 251 (0.00071%) CE patients identified during the considered period, 142 (56.6%) were females, and 109 (43.4%) were males. The highest number of CE cases was recorded in the 21–30 (27.9%) age group, followed by 31–40 (23.1%) and 41–50 (16.3%). Most of the CE patients in KPK province were members of the Afghani ethnic group (17.1%); secondarily, they were Pakistani (6.4%), while for 76.5% ethnicity data were not available. The liver (41%) and the lungs (4.8%) were the most infected organs identified among CE patients in KPK province. The present study identified CE as a significant public health problem in KPK province, and the current findings demonstrated a constant endemicity of CE during the last 15 years.

C) CE: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy). [Published]

E. granulosus s.s., associated with G1 and G3 genotypes, is endemic with high prevalence in the Mediterranean basin. The parasite's life cycle comprises definitive hosts (canids) and intermediate hosts (ruminants) and can occasionally involve humans. The main aim of this research was to confirm the diagnosis of 13 patients suspected of CE who presented different complications and needed the surgical removal of the cysts. We also wanted to understand and clarify more the diagnosis of CE in humans. For this purpose, the patients first underwent cyst evaluation by ultrasound (US), immunological analysis, and then total pericystectomy, followed by parasitological, histopathological, and molecular biology examinations of the cysts. US stadiated one CE1, one CE2, eight CE3b, one CE4, and two CE5; immunology evidenced nine positives; histopathology confirmed 11 CE cysts, of which 8 fertile presenting protoscolecocytes were identified as *E. granulosus s.s.* by molecular biology, genotyped as three G1 and four G3 by neighbor-joining (NJ) phylogenetic tree. In conclusion, the results showed that 11 patients were affected by *E. granulosus s.s.* G1 or G3, and 2 cystic neoformations were of non-parasitic origin.

D) Identification of *E. granulosus* genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays (Italy). [Published]

Different *E. granulosus s.l.* genotypes exhibit great diversity in their life cycle, host selectivity and pathogenicity. For this reason, the study of genetic variation within *Echinococcus* species is of importance for their epidemiological implication. We employed two SNP genotyping technologies to distinguish G1 and G3 *E. granulosus s.s.* genotypes. The genotypes of DNA samples (N=28) extracted from hydatid cysts of different animal species were identified by amplification and sequencing of a fragment of the mitochondrial nad5 gene. Two SYBR green and three TaqMan real time PCR assays were developed for targeting of three nad5 informative positions (SNP758, 1123, and 1380) known to be able to discriminate G1 from G3. Genotyping by SYBR Green PCR based on cycle threshold (Ct) with melting temperature (Tm) analysis and performed on SNP1123 and SNP1380 failed to identify one DNA sample. TaqMan assays for SNP758, 1123 and 1380 effectively confirmed genotype identification obtained by Sanger sequencing. Our results demonstrated that the combination of the three Taqman assays developed in this study represents a valuable and cost effective tool alternative to DNA sequencing for *E. granulosus s.s.* genotyping.

E) CE in northern Tanzania: a pilot study in Maasai livestock-keeping communities. [Published]

The aim of this study was to estimate the prevalence of human abdominal CE and the prevalence and

species/genotypes of *E. granulosus s.l.* in livestock in Maasai communities. Human CE was diagnosed by abdominal ultrasound in five villages in the Longido and Ngorongoro Districts in northern Tanzania. Infection in ruminants was evaluated through inspection in local abattoirs, followed by molecular identification of one cyst per animal, using PCR-RFLP and mPCR (see **WP3-T2-ST3**). Ultrasound was performed on 823 volunteers (N=352 in two villages in Longido District, and N=471 in three villages of Ngorongoro). Hepatic CE cases were diagnosed only in Ngorongoro (N=6; 1.3%), of which three had active cysts. Village-level prevalence of CE ranged between 0 and 2.4%. Of the 697 ruminants inspected, 34.4% had parasitic cysts. Molecular identification was achieved for 140 of the 219 (63.9%) cysts sampled. *E. granulosus s.l.* and *T. hydatigena/Cysticercus tenuicollis* were identified in 51.4% and 48.6%, respectively, of livestock cysts. *E. granulosus s.l.* was identified in livestock from both Longido (35.3% of 116 genotyped cysts) and Ngorongoro (91.2% of 34 genotyped cysts). Of the total of 72 *E. granulosus s.l.* cysts identified in livestock, 87.5% were *E. granulosus s.s.* (G1–G3), 9.7% were *E. ortleppi* (G5) and one cyst was *E. canadensis* (G6-10). The three active human cysts, which were removed surgically, were G1–G3. Multiple species/genotypes of *E. granulosus s.l.* are circulating in Maasai communities of northern Tanzania.

F) Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of CE in Sheep (Italy). [Published]

This study assessed the performances of three post-mortem laboratory methods in the diagnosis of ovine CE. In the absence of a single and accurate test as a gold standard, the results of multiple analytical tests can be combined to estimate diagnostic performance based on a Bayesian statistical approach. For this purpose, livers (N=77), and lungs (N=79) were sampled from adult sheep and examined using gross pathology, histopathology and molecular analyses. Data from the three diagnostic methods were analyzed using a Bayesian latent class analysis model to evaluate their diagnostic accuracy in terms of sensitivity (Se), specificity (Sp), positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV). The gross pathology examination revealed excellent diagnostic capabilities in diagnosing ovine CE with an Se of 99.7 (96.7–99.8), Sp of 97.5 (90.3–99.8), PPV of 97.6 (90.5–100), and NPV of 99.7 (96.5–100).

G) Comparison and evaluation of analytic and diagnostic performances of four commercial kits for the detection of antibodies of *E. granulosus* and *E. multilocularis* in human sera (Italy). [Published]

The aim of our study was to evaluate and compare four commercial diagnostic kits, based on the detection of IgG antibodies against *E. granulosus* and *E. multilocularis*. The study was performed on a total of 259 sera: the positive (N=74) and the negative (N=185) group. The following analytic and diagnostic performances of the four kits were evaluated: operator skills, specificity, sensitivity, repeatability, reproducibility, accuracy, positive and negative predictive values. Based on the parameters evaluated, all four tests demonstrated excellent quality and proved to be reliable diagnostic tools to support the clinical evaluation of human patients suspected of having CE. The four commercial assays, in our hands, presented altogether, a range of performances from good to excellent, being immunoblotting (IB) the most reliable, used as gold standard, followed by the immunochromatographic test (ICT) and finally the two enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISAs).

H) Morphological characteristics of AE and CE lesions in human liver and bone (Germany). [Published]

CE and AE are neglected infectious diseases epidemiologically and are clinically vastly different with distinct microscopic features. Because of the rareness of these zoonotic diseases, pathologists have limited diagnostic experience in the analysis of the lesions caused by *Echinococcus* tapeworms. In this study we describe the main microscopic features to be considered to characterize these lesions: laminated layer, central necrosis, growth pattern, and delineation from adjacent tissue. Moreover, immunohistology using monoclonal antibodies is of great diagnostic help in reaching a definitive diagnosis by identifying the laminated body and small particles of *E. multilocularis* (spems) and small particles of *E. granulosus* (spegs).

I) Intestinal zoonotic parasites in dogs and foxes in an *Em* endemic area in Limburg (Netherlands).

The aim is to study the northern dispersal of *Em* from the endemic region in the southern province Limburg, where the prevalence increased from 1998 to 2013 from 13% to 59%. In addition dogs were included to be tested for *Em* and a questionnaire (same of **WP3-T7**) was distributed to owners and vets. In the study area more northern from this endemic area, 113 fecal droppings were collected in

the field and tested with the MC-PCR (Maas et al., 2016). Only 2 fox droppings originating from the endemic control area were tested positive (22%). The 37 fecal droppings from the study area were negative. The other droppings were from unknown or other origin. Also a selection of dogs, hunting and eating rodents in the endemic area tested negative for Em. Although 65% of the hunting dogs were dewormed, the majority of dogs hunting on rodents were not dewormed more than 4 times a year. In conclusion there was no evidence of northern spread of Em in foxes from the endemic area, and no dogs were tested positive for Em. Although the sample size from the study area was limited.